

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the features of the translation of English sayings and proverbs means of the Uzbek language. Phraseological units act as a tool representations of the features of the national mentality, are characterized by a high cultural and national marking, contain, in addition to linguistic, extra linguistic aspects, which causes numerous difficulties when translating from one language to another. The need to convey the extra linguistic aspects of the translated construction necessitates the search for new ways of translating English proverbs and sayings into Uzbek. The article is devoted to the study of the features of the interaction of cultures in the process of implementing translation activities. The study revealed that within the framework of the linguoculturological approach, the most common ways of translating phraseological units are search equivalent, phraseological analogue. Cases of the use of Uzbek phraseological units in situations where it is absent in the original language seem to be not rare.

Keywords: proverbs, sayings, translation, phraseology, translation equivalence, the adequacy of the translation.

INTORUCTION

The proverbs are popularly defined as short expressions of popular wisdom which refer to common experience are often expressed in metaphor, alliteration, or rhyme. A proverb (from the Latin proverbium) is a simple and concrete saying popularly known and repeated, which expresses a truth, based on from generation to generation" [1, p. 27]. It is clear from the definition that proverb is not a simple unit of a language; it is a ready-made sentence that gives metaphorical meaning with words of wisdom or traditional thoughts of people or nation.

Literature review As linguist Eugene Nida noticed that in order to learn the language of a nation ,it is important to study it's culture. He emphasized that language and culture are interrelated. He explained it as follows:"Cultural factors are deeply interwoven with the language and thus are morphologically and structurally reflected in the forms of the language ". The scientist of linguistics Veronika Telia (

PhD,Dr.habil.,Prof) calls proverbs as "direct cultural signs " and believes that proverbs are factors that reflect the culture of the people. In Telia's (PhD,Dr.habil.,Prof) opinion each proverb is a mirror that people's way of life can be fully expressed .She wrote:“After having described the interaction between language, culture and proverbs,seems also important to mention the ways in which culture is implemented through language. Each culture has a set of proverbs that could be defined as basic, when they enter the lexicon and the language, it is possible they act as “direct cultural signs”.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proverbs of each country are different from one another, depending on the history of creation and the ways which people express in their lifestyle. There are similarities between proverbs in English and Uzbek. This attitude is that when we analyze proverbs in various ways [Palmer, 1981]:

1. Morphological;
2. Lexical;
3. Etiological;
4. Stylistic.

We can clearly see differences between them in the analysis. One of the first differences between the two languages is the images used in them. In many English proverbs, the expression of human nature is often used by animal images: Eagles do not catch flies (eagles do not hold flies). The higher the monkey climbs the more he shows his tail (the more the monkey looks up, the more tail it looks) In contrast, Uzbek proverbs refer as a simple human lifestyle without getting an animal image. For instance: - O’xshatmasdan uchratmas (They do not meet who do not look like each other). Here, we should mention a few variations in translating proverbs from one language into common sense or the practical experience of humanity (Latin, 2011). The linguist W. Mieder defines a proverb in his book: “A proverb is a short, generally known sentence of the folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed and memorisable form and which is handed down another. It helps to translate proverbs from the English language to the Uzbek language through these types of translation. There is equivalent form of the above mentioned Uzbek proverb in English: O’xshatmasdan uchratmas (They do not meet who do not look like each other)- Birds of a feather flock together.

- There are several types of proverbs that can be translated into other languages :
- Using phraseological Equivalent;
 - Absolute Equivalent; - Similar Equivalent.
 - Use direct translation

There are the same proverbs in English and Uzbek which can be translated into absolute style. A watched pot never boils - Kutilgan qozon qaynamas. Wisdom is the beauty of men - odam bezagi aql (beauty of man is his wisdom). Manners make the man - insonni fazilatlar ulug'laydi (Manners earn reputation for man). In conclusion, many Uzbek's and English's proverbs on Evil have the same meaning. Only words in both languages are different. Proverbs that have different meanings in the process of semantically analysis are observed the same meaning. In all English and Uzbek proverbs evil is shown as the most vile and disgusting side. We can mention that there are some proverbs which are very difficult to translate, in some cases almost impossible, as they are narrowly linked to the cultural and social system of the society. Comparison of two nations' proverbs reveals that proverbs reflect the rich historical experience of the people, ideas which related with work, lifestyle and culture of people. Using proverbs correct and appropriate makes speech unique originality and the expressiveness.

CONCLUSION

Proverbs are the transmission of people's linguistic phrases and cultural manners from one generation into another. That's why the treatment of rendering proverbs must be careful, precise, and not to be expected literally. Not to forget to take into account the proverb cultural, religious, historical background to use the appropriate translation method, hence, achieving a balance between form and content, and also rendering the information the proverb wants to give successfully into the other language without losing the essence of the its meaning.

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